

Organisation ETT SpA
Department R&D Unit

NAUTILOS

D8.5

Interoperability services and catalogues

Date: 21/12/2021
Doc. Version: 2.2

10.5281/zenodo.7224664

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000825 (NAUTILOS). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Deliverable Title	Interoperability services and catalogues
Work Package Title	Data Management
Deliverable number	D8.5
Description	This deliverable describes the services and catalogues. It considers both common interoperability recommendations and recent data publishing tools and techniques, as well as how to provide long term visibility of the NAUTILOS contribution to global data exchange.
Lead Beneficiary	ETT SpA
Lead Authors	Antonio Novellino, Federica Colombo
Contributors	
Submitted by	Federica Colombo
Doc. Version (Revision number)	[2.2]
Sensitivity (Security):	Public
Date:	[21/12/2021]
doi	10.5281/zenodo.7224664

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

Name	Role	Action	Date
Gabriele Pieri	Coordinator	Review	06/11/21
Armindo Torres	Technical Innovation Manager	Review	06/11/21
Gabriele Pieri Flavio Martins Armindo Torres	Coordinator/WP manager	Final Approval	21/12/2021

Document history:

The Document Author is authorized to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarized in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
0.1	31/08/2021	Federica Colombo	First draft
1.0	30/09/2021	Federica Colombo	First full version
2.0	30/11/2021	Federica Colombo	Restructuring of table of content and document completion
2.1	02/12/2021	Antonio Novellino	Final draft
2.2	21/12/2021	Federica Colombo	Validated document

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in <location>.

Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report	x
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This report forms part of the deliverables from the NAUTILOS project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000825. The Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of the content of this publication.

NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <http://www.nautilus-project.eu>.

COPYRIGHT

© NAUTILOS Consortium. Copies of this publication – also of extracts thereof – may only be made with reference to the publisher.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	4
COPYRIGHT	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
LIST OF FIGURES	7
LIST OF TABLES	7
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	8
1. INTRODUCTION	9
2. NAUTILOS DATA INFRASTRUCTURE AND INTEROPERABILITY	10
3. NAUTILOS INTEROPERABILITY SERVICES AND CATALOGUES	15
3.1. SERVICES.....	15
3.1.1. ERDDAP.....	15
Examples and guidelines to deploy ERDDAP	15
3.1.2. GeoServer	17
Example on how to install GeoSERVER and how to publish a simple layer.....	17
3.2. CATALOGUES	18
3.2.1. GEONETWORK	18
3.2.2. How to set up and configure GeoNetwork.....	18
3.3. Digital Object Identifier	19
3.3.1. SEANOE.....	21
3.3.2. PANGAEA.....	21
3.3.3. Zenodo.....	22
3.3.4. ARGO floats	22
3.3.5. Oceanographic cruises.....	23
4. HOW TO INTEROPERATE WITH NAUTILOS STAKEHOLDERS	24
5. APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS	25

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ability to integrate across such a management landscape, in support of ocean research, depends critically on the widespread adoption of data interoperability standards. Interoperability can be defined as the “degree to which two or more systems, products or components can exchange information and use the information that has been exchanged” (ISO/IEC/IEEE, 2017). It is the ability by which coupled systems can communicate and exchange data via common formats and protocols and also meaningfully interpret and reproducibly act on exchanged data.

Novel data management approaches have to start from enhancing data handling through more widespread adoption of community data standards and well-designed data management plans based on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles so that data is machine-readable.

Although interoperability is not a characteristic of a single data file or dataset, enhancing interoperability means improving data sharing between scientists, industry and governments. Each of these players are interested, for instance, in obtaining data for scientific research, for assimilation into a numerical model, or to create a web-based visualisation tool. According to each specific use, it is necessary to provide all the available data and extensive metadata to ensure that users understand as much as possible about how the data were generated, and make data accessible or downloadable by means of different data delivery channels (e.g. FTP, webAPI, etc.).

The data generated within the NAUTILOS project are meant to be highly complementary to the existing observing systems, and therefore all data and metadata need to be standardised and harmonised to meet interoperability standards.

Nevertheless, it is important to show the provenience of this data (i.e. the NAUTILOS project) and have the proper citation tools in order to let NAUTILOS project to track its scientific impact and third parties data use.

The present document outlines the standards and best practices on data format and metadata that are being adopted during the project implementation to ensure and facilitate interoperability and harmonisation of the new observations generated with the already available data disseminated towards the well-established data dissemination infrastructures.

The services and catalogues used in NAUTILOS to implement interoperability and how to deploy them in practice are also described.

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Roles and processes involved in data lifecycle (Buck et al. 2019)	11
Figure 2 NAUTILOS data layer workflow designed	12
Figure 3 NAUTILOS infrastructure layers and modules	13

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Backend tools used by NAUTILOS main stakeholders	24
--	----

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
CDI	Common Data Index
CF convention	Climate and Forecast convention
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring System
DAC	Data Archive Centre
DMP	Data management policy
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, re-usable
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GTS	Global Telecommunication System
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
JERICO	Joint European Research Infrastructure of Coastal Observatories
MEDIN	Marine Environmental Data and Information Network
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NVS	NERC vocabulary service
ODV	Ocean Data View
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
QC	Quality control
SOOS	Southern Ocean Observing System
TAC	Thematic Assembly Centre

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of NAUTILOS is to fill in existing marine observation and modelling gaps through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers for physical (salinity, temperature), chemical (inorganic carbon, nutrients, oxygen), and biological (phytoplankton, zooplankton, marine macrofauna) essential ocean variables (EOVs), in addition to micro- and nano-plastics, to improve our understanding of environmental change and anthropogenic impacts.

A specific technical objective of the NAUTILOS project is to appropriately collate, process, and archive all primary environmental data generated during the project to ensure that they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR).

The achievement of this objective requires the development of an end-to-end information system and infrastructure for both data management (internal to the project) and data transfer towards well-established repository services and tools (e.g. National Oceanographic Data Centres and thematic and international data assembly repositories, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Services). It also requires i) the preparation of data and metadata following commonly agreed standards and FAIR principles, ii) the establishment of mechanisms for integration and interoperability of heterogeneous data and production of open-access data, and iii) the processing of environmental data appended with the necessary sensor specification, validation, calibration data, and field operation details to enable stand-alone data reuse.

The present document outlines the standards and best practices on data format and metadata that are being adopted during the project implementation to ensure and facilitate interoperability and harmonisation of the new observations generated with the already available data disseminated towards the well-established data dissemination infrastructures.

The services and catalogues used in NAUTILOS to implement interoperability are also described.

2. NAUTILOS DATA INFRASTRUCTURE AND INTEROPERABILITY

Ocean data are diverse in type, coverage, and extent. They include multi-variate observational data from near-real time in situ and remote sensing platforms, data from research cruises, and data from numerical models. While the possibilities are immense, sizeable obstacles currently impede global, interdisciplinary, and inclusive progress. For example, the majority of oceanographic data available today are downloadable from web portals which have tailored their search interfaces and data products to highly specialised consumers, limiting generalised use and cross-boundary innovation.

Data are also often available from disparate networks, in a variety of formats and with sparse or poorly structured metadata. Collectively, these issues greatly slow down the discovery and use of ocean data, as well as the generation of downstream products and knowledge.

In this context, interoperability is essential to enable data to be used, reused, preserved, and integrated, building a federated system in which components can be exchanged. To achieve this, standardisation of formats, distribution protocols and metadata is necessary.

The ability to integrate across such a management landscape, in support of ocean research, depends critically on the widespread adoption of data interoperability standards. Interoperability can be defined as the “degree to which two or more systems, products or components can exchange information and use the information that has been exchanged” (ISO/IEC/IEEE, 2017). It is the ability by which coupled systems can communicate and exchange data via common formats and protocols and also meaningfully interpret and reproducibly act on exchanged data.

A data life cycle diagram is shown in Figure 1 to provide context on the various stages in data workflows from sensor to user, on the organisations involved and what structural units are required to deliver the workflow (Buck et al., 2019).

Figure 1 Roles and processes involved in data lifecycle (Buck et al. 2019)

Novel data management approaches have to start from enhancing data handling through more widespread adoption of community data standards and well-designed data management plans based on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles so that data is machine-readable.

Although interoperability is not a characteristic of a single data file or dataset, enhancing interoperability means improving data sharing between scientists, industry and governments. Each of these players are interested, for instance, in obtaining data for scientific research, for assimilation into a numerical model, or to create a web-based visualisation tool. According to each specific use, it is necessary to provide all the available data and extensive metadata to ensure that users understand as much as possible about how the data were generated, and make data accessible or downloadable by means of different data delivery channels (e.g. FTP, webAPI, etc.).

Another key element for enabling proper data consumption is the application of quality procedures. Quality data typically result from the application of community best practices across their lifecycle. The usability of even the best data is compromised without well-structured metadata and descriptions of provenance. Ensuring the integrity of the data (avoiding data corruption) is especially important for data that are to be stored in perpetuity and intended for future reuse. Data integrity has to be transparently confirmed and well-documented throughout data lifecycle. This documentation needs to be readily accessible to the public as part of standard provenance metadata.

The data generated within the NAUTILOS project are meant to be highly complementary to the existing observing systems, and therefore all data and metadata need to be standardised and harmonised to meet interoperability standards.

Nevertheless, it is important to show the provenience of this data (i.e. the NAUTILOS project) and have the proper citation tools in order to let NAUTILOS project to track its scientific impact and third parties data use.

To facilitate interoperability, NAUTILOS infrastructure is going to have a logical layer designed to manage data and data products, another one to organise them to offer the services, and an application layer i.e., the end-user interface (and features) to access and use the developed and provided services (see D8.3 for details).

The data layer is in charge for ingesting datasets and is able to make available data in different formats, like csv, txt, netcdf, etc.

NAUTILOS data infrastructure manages two levels of data disclosure rights: a private level that is open to partners only for internal data exchange and application of needed quality checks, and a public level that receives data from the private level and makes data open to all the NAUTILOS stakeholders.

Figure 2 NAUTILOS data layer workflow designed

NAUTILOS infrastructure offers the partner a framework to exchange data, cross validate new sensors and methodologies (Figure 2). Data and datasets are then harmonised according to common standards and made ready for dissemination (service layer). At this level, as recommended by the IOC data management plan manual, (some) datasets can be stored individually and be given a DOI (a unique, persistent digital identifier). Notably a DOI is also important when datasets are used from large data bases that are subjected to changes, e.g., annual reprocessing, versioning, etc.

A single dataset source may be integrated in more products and the service layer organizes data within the NAUTILOS datasets and data products publication services and catalogues (ERDDAP, GeoServer, GeoNetwork). The application layer implements the NAUTILOS interfaces (map portal) and other machine-to-machine services (Figure 3).

Figure 3 NAUTILOS infrastructure layers and modules

As described in D8.2 and D8.3, there are three main elements for implementing data interoperability: data format, metadata and data services. To improve data provenience visibility and NAUTILOS data citation, the project is designing the adoption digital object identifier.

In brief:

- **Data format:** NAUTILOS is collecting a number of biogeochemical, biological and EOVS by developing innovative and more accurate sensors. To maximise the usability and the value of the project's outcome, NAUTILOS data will be made available in standard transport formats, i.e., netCDF, txt, HD5, wav (see D8.2 for details).
- **Metadata** are the envelope describing the collected data. Metadata are the key element for enabling interoperability and reusability of data. As described in D8.2, NAUTILOS adopts ISO standards and controlled and linked vocabularies.
- **Data services** are the operational tools to implement machine-to-machine (M2M) FAIR services. As described above, NAUTILOS has adopted a data interoperability infrastructure that is based on a combination of open software tools (ERDDAP, GeoServer, GeoNetwork) that implements common standards for M2M connections, and are being adopted by the wider European and international data infrastructure community (GOOS, EMODnet, CMEMS, etc).
- **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its

DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata.

3. NAUTILOS INTEROPERABILITY SERVICES AND CATALOGUES

The ability to access and search metadata for marine science data is a key requirement for answering fundamental principles of data management, making data FAIR. In order to address the requirements of the Findable aspect of FAIR data, a dataset needs to be described by rich metadata in a searchable resource and the dataset shall be assigned a clearly labelled persistent, unique identifier. Therefore, there is a need for a modular approach to data cataloguing, designed to meet a number of requirements. Modularity is required in order to represent datasets, projects or programmes and other data resources within the catalogue system in other cross-disciplinary topics. This section provides the user with NAUTILOS strategy to set up the catalogue and the services, how to implement and deploy those services and how to use them.

3.1. SERVICES

3.1.1. ERDDAP

ERDDAP data server is open-source software written in Java that provides a platform through which data can be shared between partners and also published more widely. Developed out of NOAA's Monterey Laboratory, the platform-agnostic ERDDAP, or the Environmental Research Division's Data Access Program, builds upon the open-source ideals of the OPeNDAP, WCS, Sensor Observation Service (SOS) and OBIS standards. It offers a consistent, yet an easy-to-use way of downloading or viewing scientific data in a variety of formats. Through all of this, ERDDAP also provides the ability to generate RESTful web API links in a relatively straightforward manner, which makes the process of integrating data into web-based applications simple. ERDDAP data server supports several common data file formats (html table, netcdf, csv, txt, mat, json, etc.) and output files are created on-the-fly in any of this format. ERDDAP implements FGDC Web Accessible Folder (WAF) with FGDC-STD-001-1998 and ISO 19115 WAF with ISO 19115-2/19139.

The end result is that users can access data from multiple datastores from a single portal or API while the data remains within the control of the experts (data centres). A federated system should always serve the latest version of the data, thus solving the "multiple copies" issues found in a traditional distributed system. While federation between the same software (ERDDAP to ERDDAP) is straightforward, federating between different systems using different software is more complex and relies on mapped or, preferably, synchronised and co-developed vocabularies which describe the data itself in a machine-readable way.

The GOOS Observation Coordination Group (OCG), coordinating the activities of the global ocean observing networks, is working to improve data interoperability between and within the various observing networks. The OCG is actively promoting the use of ERDDAP as a key tool towards interoperability of global ocean datasets.

Examples and guidelines to deploy ERDDAP

A prerequisite to prepare the environment is the installation of Apache web server, Java 8 and Tomcat. The detailed ERDDAP installation guide is available at <https://coastwatch.pfeg.noaa.gov/erddap/download/setup.html>

In brief, to install ERDDAP:

1. Download latest ERDDAP WAR file, place it in the Tomcat web app directory and wait for the extraction and deployment;

2. Download **erddapContent.zip** in a folder containing the needed content for the ERDDAP web app and properly set **-DerddapContentDirectory** option in CATALINA_OPTS envi var;
3. Configure the ERDDAP service **setup.xml** file by editing at least:
 - **bigParentDirectory**: folder for ERDDAP caching, flagging and data information retraining. Must be a folder with lot of space and sufficient I/O speed to ensure ERDDAP optimal performance;
 - **http / https URL** for external server expose;
 - Admin email and work information for management.
4. Set up **ProxyPass** in Apache to access the ERDDAP service;
5. Configure the ERDDAP service datasets.xml that contains:
 - ERDDAP home page layout and options;
 - All metadata information and link to the physical data location.

Datasets.xml is divided in two parts:

1. ERDDAP home page layout and options;
2. ERDDAP datasets metadata content: every content may be Table or Grid.

Datasets live into the tag and there are two ways to add them:

1. Manual compilation of the dataset tag metadata hierarchy (for example, when the data that is going to add has no metadata directly associated (for ex. CSV tables);
2. Automated compilation using ERDDAP-provided data import tools in WEB-INF folder (for example, when using already well formatted data, such as netCDF).

To generate a rough draft of a dataset XML for a comma separated csv file in the /u00/data/ path, one can use the GenerateDatasetsXml.sh script in an interactive way or use this command line: `./GenerateDatasetsXml.sh EDDTableFromAsciiFiles /u00/data/.*\..csvc /u00/data/sampleFile.csv ISO-8859-1.`

More information is available at:

<https://coastwatch.pfeg.noaa.gov/erddap/download/setupDatasetsXml.html>

3.1.2. GeoServer

GeoServer implements several Open Geospatial Consortium protocols including:

- Web Map Service (WMS), to provide georeferenced maps of the relevant measurements;
- Web Feature Service (WFS), to provide standard download services for the relevant measurements, with support to time parameters and other capabilities. Through this interface users are able to integrate NAUTILOS datasets in their GIS applications.

Example on how to install GeoSERVER and how to publish a simple layer

As for ERDDAP, the installation of GeoServer requires Apache, Tomcat and Java 8. Detailed instructions are available at <https://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/index.html>

For instance, to publish a shapefile with GeoServer:

1. Create a workspace to group similar layers together
(<https://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/gettingstarted/shapefile-quickstart/index.html>)
2. Once the workspace is created, add a new store. The store tells GeoServer how to connect to the shapefile.
3. Publish the layer

To visualise a layer on a map using OpenLayers, one can use the OpenLayers.Layer.WMS object like this:

```
var customLayer = new OpenLayers.Layer.WMS(  
    "Name custom layer",  
    "https://geoserver.emodnet-physics.eu/geoserver/emodnet/ows",  
    {  
        "format": "image/png",  
        "transparent": true,  
        "layers": ["EP_PLATFORMS_AR"]  
    },  
    { isBaseLayer: false, opacity: 1 }  
);
```

3.2. CATALOGUES

A data catalogue is therefore needed to make NAUTILOS data and metadata accessible in standard formats, allowing interoperability with other ocean data catalogues.

3.2.1. GEONETWORK

NAUTILOS data catalogue is going to be based on the GeoNetwork application. GeoNetwork, based on an open source (GNOS) project, is a free and open source (FOSS) cataloguing application for spatially-referenced resources (<https://geonetwork-opensource.org/>), implementing international standards about services and protocols (International Organization for Standardization Technical Commission, ISO/TC211 and the OGC). GeoNetwork provides an easy-to-use web interface to search geospatial data across multiple catalogues, managing different resources at the same time, by ensuring the spatial exchanges and sharing, managing and publishing metadata and spatial data. The search provides full-text search as well as faceted search on keywords, resource types, organisations, scale, etc. The catalogue is able to describe geospatial layers, services, maps and also non geographic datasets.

GeoNetwork implements WxS, OGC, ISO standards: the metadata editor supports ISO 19115/119/110 standards used for spatial resources and also Dublin Core format usually used for open data portals.

Online editing of metadata is based on a powerful template system and directories of information (eg. contacts, thesaurus). This system allows data querying using a huge volume of metadata from different environments and provides a web-based interactive map viewer. Moreover, using this software allows anyone to independently discover and exploit the dataset, without any intermediary.

3.2.2. How to set up and configure GeoNetwork

As for ERDDAP and Geoserver, the installation of GeoNetwork requires Apache, Tomcat and Java 8. Detailed instructions are available at <https://geonetwork-opensource.org/manuals/trunk/en/install-guide/index.html>

In brief, to install GeoNetwork:

1. Download the desired geonetwork.war from <https://geonetwork-opensource.org/downloads.html>
2. Copy the WAR file into the webapp folder of Tomcat.
3. If started, Tomcat will automatically deploy the application. If not, start Tomcat to deploy.

To create a new record in Geonetwork (<https://geonetwork-opensource.org/manuals/trunk/en/user-guide/index.html>):

1. From the home page, go to the contribute section or directly click on add new record menu
2. From the metadata template list, select a template (see Managing templates), choose a group from the dropdown and click 'Create'
3. Complete the fields provided by default in the template
4. Create an image of your data to illustrate it in the search results

3.3. DIGITAL OBJECT IDENTIFIER

A number of environmental research data repositories including ocean datasets are developing within research communities (Waide et al., 2017). Their role is to mobilize these data, hold a digital copy of them and make them FAIR. Although much data from these repositories are available today through online means, there are major challenges in discovering and reusing these data for synthesis research and meta-analyses, one of which being the non-interoperable state of repositories. Open access data repositories that work together and provide a common scaffolding for data deposition, discovery, and reuse can help mitigate this dilemma by providing a similar experience for both data producers and data consumers across repositories.

Therefore, repositories should ensure that each published package represents a coherent collection of data or research output so that each package represents a citable unit. All data packages should include a document that aggregates its members by referencing their globally unique identifiers.

One of the key means for enabling interoperability among data repositories involves the use of globally unique, persistent, web-resolvable identifiers and the **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** provides a system for persistent and actionable identification and interoperable exchange of managed information on digital networks:

- Rationalize data citation: if a resource editor changes, the URL of the landing page of the DOI will be updated. The bibliographic citation of the DOI remains valid.
- Simplify data access: the landing page of a DOI offers a direct access to data through an HTTP/FTP link. As the data associated to a publication is publicly available, a reader can check the publication against the DOI data, increasing the publication credibility.
- Provide traceability on data usage: the publications that cite a data set with a DOI are easy to track in bibliographic surveys. A comprehensive bibliographic survey will increase the notability of the scientist or infrastructure that published the data set with a DOI.

Considering all these features of the DOI system, its application to the datasets generated during NAUTILOS project implementation is therefore of paramount importance in order to ensure interoperability of the project outcomes. Using a range of persistent identifiers can contextualise the data by linking them to related outputs, people and projects. They also maximise their discoverability, reach and connectivity.

NAUTILOS datasets are expected to be dynamic, i.e., they will receive regularly new data (e.g., monthly, annually) or get updated with advances in methodology or processing methods, to generate a dataset revision. With data evolving over time, it is important for users to be able to consistently refer to specific data collected or used in an analysis or paper. The ability to specifically identify and access an exact revision of data is critical for ensuring reproducibility of analyses utilizing those data. However, when an older version is accessed, the repository should highlight the fact that a newer version is available. In most cases this functionality is achieved by assigning a new identifier (e.g., DOI) to every version and keeping all versions accessible while general searches would present only the most recent version. Relationships between revisions of data should be preserved by a repository and when making such information available to users, the relationships should utilize already defined concepts intended for such purpose (e.g., a versioning system like software versioning).

The choice on what granularity to use for DOIs depends on data and their usage. A strategy may be defined based on the level of aggregation of data that are generally used in a publication, as the DOIs main objective is to facilitate and improve the reliability of data citation. If a DOI is assigned at a measurement level and if the related publication manages thousands of these measurements, it will be difficult to cite properly the thousand associated DOIs. In that case, DOIs are probably not properly assigned.

So far, two distinct approaches and subsequent workflows for the identification of datasets have emerged. One approach consists in developing an interface for researchers that allows them to mint or place a mediated request for a DOI name for their data collection. Another approach is to mint DOIs for data collections that have already been curated and are maintained by research data administrators. The latter does not require liaison with researchers though it will be important to communicate the DOI concept and its use in data citation. The two different approaches require different workflows and communication strategies though it is likely that as DOI implementation develops, an institution will support both workflows.

There are several data publishing repositories in Europe that propose free publication of research data with DOIs, such as Seanoë (<http://www.seanoë.org>), Pangaea (<https://www.pangaea.de>), Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>). They all use DataCite to register DOIs.

The following paragraphs present on the approach of these three main systems as well as the strategy that has been implemented by consolidated and structured international network programs (e.g. ARGO)

3.3.1. SEANOE

SEANOE (SEA scieNtific Open data Edition) is a publisher of scientific data in the field of marine sciences. It is operated by Sismer (Scientific Information Systems for the Sea), Ifremer's service in charge of managing marine databases and information systems. The long-term preservation of data filed in SEANOE is ensured by Ifremer infrastructure.

Seanoe allows an embargo limited to 2 years on a dataset: a DOI is assigned to data with restricted access during for instance the review period of a scientific publication.

Data published in SEANOE are also automatically duplicated to the [EMODnet Data Ingestion](#) portal so that marine data centers of the EMODnet Ingestion network will be informed about the existence and the availability of datasets published in SEANOE.

For managing different versions of datasets, Seanoe provides two choices:

- All versions of the data set are directly available
- Access to old versions is restricted: previous versions are accessible via a request to a service desk. It is then possible to ensure the reproducibility of an experiment based on an obsolete version, but access to an obsolete version of the data set is intentional and not accidental. (Example: <http://doi.org/10.17882/43749>)

It is also possible to set a key/fragment to each version managed in a single DOI and then cite a specific version with the DOI associated to the key/fragment (see Argo example).

Seanoe provides an automatic calculation of downloads statistics once a year.

3.3.2. PANGAEA

PANGAEA is an open access library aimed at archiving, publishing and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research.

Data citation and DOI are defined in three steps during the publication process:

- registry status *will be registered*, then
 - registry status *registration is in the lead time* with DOI registration in progress for **30 days** followed by
 - registry status *registered* after transfer of the DOI to the DOI-registry > DOI can be resolved globally, e.g. at <https://doi.org/>
1. If a data set is imported and the status is set to *validated*, its internal ID can only be resolved as a **preliminary DOI** through *doi.pangaea.de* (PANGAEAs own DOI resolver). In the citation, the data set is identified as **Dataset #738509**
 2. If a data set status is set to *published*, the internal ID is changed to a global resolvable **technical DOI** four weeks after the last edit and the data set gets the status [citable](#). In the citation, the data set is identified as **Dataset #738509 (DOI registration in progress)**, changing after four weeks to **doi:10.1594/PANGAEA.82361** which can be resolved globally.
 3. On request the dataset can be defined as an official **data publication** and is thus added to the library catalogue

The DOI workflow depends on the type of platform. Some examples of DOI attribution policies are given below.

3.3.3. Zenodo

The OpenAIRE project was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research. CERN, an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided this capability and Zenodo was launched in May 2013.

Zenodo supports DOI versioning, that enables users to update the record's files after they have been made public and researchers to easily cite either specific versions of a record or to cite, via a top-level DOI, all the versions of a record.

When a user publishes an upload on Zenodo for the first time, Zenodo registers two DOIs:

- a DOI representing the **specific version** of the record.
- a DOI representing **all of the versions** of the record.

Afterwards, Zenodo registers a DOI for every new version of the upload.

This is best illustrated by an example of a software package. If the software has been released in two versions (v1.0 and v1.1) on Zenodo, then the following DOIs would have been registered:

- **v1.0 (specific version):** 10.5281/zenodo.60943
- **v1.1 (specific version):** 10.5281/zenodo.800648
- **Concept (all versions):** 10.5281/zenodo.705645

The first two DOIs for versions **v1.0** and **v.1.1** represent the specific versions of the software. The last DOI represents all the versions of the given software package, i.e., the concept of the software package and the ensemble of versions.

Tracking of datasets usage is possible also with Zenodo. It tracks two types of events:

1. Visits to a record page.
2. Downloads of a file.

For both types of events, Zenodo tracks:

1. **Visitor:** An anonymized visitor ID.
2. **Visitor type:** If the request was made by a) human, b) machine or c) robot.
3. **Country:** The country of origin of the request (based on the IP address).
4. **Referrer:** The referrer domain.

3.3.4. ARGO floats

Argo data are collected and disseminated by Argo GDACs (Global Data Assembly Centres) through their FTP sites. The available data from these FTP sites are continuously changing: data are added and updated every day. To allow reproducibility of studies with Argo data, a snapshot of the entire data set is preserved every month. The snapshot contains all the Argo data available at the time of the snapshot creation. Initially, according to the suggestion of DataCite to include dynamic data, a DOI was set to describe the overall data set. In addition, specific DOIs were assigned to each monthly snapshot. To satisfy the Argo group that did not want to inflate the number of DOIs and to follow the new recommendations of the Research Data Alliance (RDA), a new single Argo DOI was then published using Seano. This unique DOI quotes either the global data set or a specific snapshot. Each monthly snapshot is uploaded in Seano that assigns a URL and a key.

The citation of a specific snapshot is done by adding the key preceded by the # character to the DOI.

This new single Argo DOI offers an easier identification of publications as they simply cite the unique DOI. The snapshots are archived in Seano, which guarantees for long term. The solution developed for publishing the Argo data in Seano can be implemented without additional development for any type of marine data.

3.3.5. Oceanographic cruises

The cruise managers are required to post a Cruise Summary Report (CSR) at the end of the cruise to Sismer. Sismer manages the CSR and records the metadata of the cruise in a database. Then Sismer assigns a DOI through the DataCite API. The DOI LandingPage is built by merging the information gathered from multiple databases. The LandingPages are updated daily in batch. The DOIs information is made available in the catalogue of French oceanographic cruises.

Some oceanographic cruises are part of multiannual programmes. A specific type of DOI has been attributed to series of cruises. A scientist can publish on and cite a series of cruises with the “series” DOI, or/and cite specific DOIs of cruises. The LandingPage of the DOI on a series of cruises and its associated specific LandingPage cruise DOIs provides cross-links, useful to Internet users who will navigate between series and individual cruises.

4. HOW TO INTEROPERATE WITH NAUTILOS STAKEHOLDERS

Table 1 Backend tools used by NAUTILOS main stakeholders

Stakeholder	Backend tools	Reference documentation
EMODnet Biology	OBIS/GBIF	https://www.emodnet-biology.eu/sites/emodnet-biology.eu/files/public/tutorials/Guidance_How_to_share_biodiversity_data.pdf
EMODnet Chemistry	Common Data Index (CDI) Data Discovery and Access service	https://www.emodnet-chemistry.eu/doi/documents/Updated-Guidelines-CDI_EMODnetChemistry4_10072_020.pdf
EMODnet Physics	ERDDAP	https://github.com/EMODnet-Physics/
EMODnet Seabed Habitats	OGC services	https://www.emodnet-seabedhabitats.eu/media/1840/accessing_emodnet_sbh_tutorial.pdf
SeaDataNet	Common Data Index (CDI) Data Discovery and Access service	https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata/CDI-Common-Data-Index
PANGAEA	World Data System (WDS), WIS, GEOSS, OpenAIRE, GBIF, OBIS, GFBio, DataONE	https://www.pangaea.de/about/services.php

5. APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	Use of Observations & Measurements and Sensor Web Enablement-related standards in INSPIRE. INSPIRE Maintenance and Implementation Group (MIG), 2016.	https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/id/document/tg/d2.9-o%26m-swe
2	F. Galgani, A. Giorgetti, M. Vinci, M. Le Moigne, G. Moncoiffe, A. Brosich, M.E. Molina Jack, M. Lipizer, N. Holdsworth, R. Schlitzer, G. Hanke, D. Schaap, M.D.M Chaves Montero, 2020, Proposal for gathering and managing data sets on marine micro-litter on a European scale, 03/06/2020, 34 pp., DOI: 10.6092/8ce4e8b7-f42c-4683-9ece-c32559606dbd	https://www.emodnet-chemistry.eu/repository/Proposal-EMODnet-TG-ML-Micro-Litter-Data-Gathering-03062020.pdf
3	Underwater Soundscape and Modeling Metadata Standard (Version 1.0), Atlantic Deepwater Ecosystem Observatory Network (ADEON): An Integrated System for Long-Term Monitoring of Ecological and Human Factors on the Outer Continental Shelf.	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6792359.v2
4	Proposal to form the GOOS network, Animal borne ocean sensors, 2020. AniBOS	
5	Tsontos, V. M., C. Lam, and S. C. Arms. 2020. netCDF templates for electronic tagging data. JPL URS CL:19-6563	6510.6084/m6569.figshare.10159820
6	Buck JJH, Bainbridge SJ, Burger EF, Kraberg AC, Casari M, Casey KS, Darroch L, Rio JD, Metfies K, Delory E, Fischer PF, Gardner T, Heffernan R, Jirka S, Kokkinaki A, Loebel M, Buttigieg PL, Pearlman JS and Schewe I (2019) Ocean Data Product Integration Through Innovation-The Next Level of Data Interoperability. <i>Front. Mar. Sci.</i> 6:32.	10.3389/fmars.2019.00032
7	Waide, RB, Brunt, JW and Servilla, MS. 2017. Demystifying the Landscape of Ecological Data Repositories in the United States. <i>BioScience</i> , 67(12): 1044–1051. Oxford University Press.	https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/bix117
8	Gries, C., Budden, A., Laney, C., O'Brien, M., Servilla, M., Sheldon, W., ... Vieglais, D. (2018). Facilitating and Improving Environmental Research Data Repository Interoperability. <i>Data Science Journal</i> , 17, 22.	http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2018-022